

8T – The Coupling Constants series Orthogonal Curvatures

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July 18, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the entities of the 8T as net curvature oriented to a certain direction, it is possible to intersect the idea of orthogonality and inner product with the 8T and in particular the coupling constants series. Anti-matter and matter are curvatures oriented to inverse direction, causing release of energy, or the vanishing of curvature on the varying matrix tensor.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those equations are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Fermions were proven in the 8T to be the result of discretizing and partitioning the term of arbitrary variations that must vanish in equation (1.31):

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.31)$$

In addition, bosons are net curvature of discrete prime amount, isomorphic to prime numbers or one. Supported by the coupling constants series in equations (1.4) to (1.43).

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.32)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.43)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up to this point, reader is probably familiar with everything as those are the fundamentals of the 8T, and from this point, we have a completely new paper. We have proven that the coupling constants series is the same under sign reversal, which gives rise to the existence of anti-matter.

$$\left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \left[-2N_3 - \frac{1}{2} \right] - \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.45)$$

Since the one-half is a representation of net curvature on the manifold, and the electron is represented by the one-half inside the bracket, we can represent the positron and the electron as curvature oriented in orthogonal way, leading to an inner product that is zero.

$$\langle \delta g_i | -\delta g_i \rangle = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

The fact their inner product is zero, is indicating an energy release. The pairing can be thought as two orthogonal pulls leading to peer pressure on the matrix tensor. such pressure could lead to the matrix be ripped apart, and by doing so we will observe a gate to the base space of raw energy, the Ricci flow, given by $\partial g / \partial t$ on the main equation (1). We can use equation (1.46) with leptons as elements of the inner product such as the electron and positron:

$$\langle +3_i | -3_i \rangle = 0$$

In addition, at the same time with bosons:

$$\langle \gamma_i | \gamma_i^- \rangle = 0$$

Which are net curvature unbounded on the matrix tensor in contrast to the electron, bounded by the nuclei, given by the fact it is within the bracket. From that point of view, it is clear that Anti-Matter is the perfect source of energy as it is leading to a pure release of energy, given by the orthogonality of the curvatures participating as given by (1.46). Notice that the summation is holding in (1.46), we can eliminate clusters of inverse curvature elements as long as the index is the same.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)